

TIME-TO-FAILURE PREDICTIONS FOR POLYMER LAMINATES IN FIRE

P.T. Summers¹, B.Y. Lattimer¹, S. Feih^{2,3}

¹Virginia Polytechnic Institute & State University
Blacksburg, VA 24061, USA
psummrs@vt.edu

²School of Aerospace, Mechanical & Manufacturing Engineering,
RMIT University, Australia

³Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures Ltd (CRC-ACS),
Australia 3Defence Science & Technology Organisation, Australia

SUMMARY

A one-dimensional thermo-mechanical model was developed to predict the thermal response and mechanical failure of polymer laminates exposed to fire conditions. A decomposition model was linked with an eccentrically loaded beam model. Maximum stress is compared with the instantaneous compressive strength to determine the time-to-failure.

Keywords: Composite, strength, modelling, furnace test, compressive loading

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) composite materials are being considered for structural applications on the topside of naval and commercial surface ships [1]. FRP composite materials are being considered for these applications in part because of the weight savings, lower construction costs, and improved life cycle costs. Though the FRP composite materials are designed to have the required structural response for strength under normal operating conditions, the structural performance of the composite degrades rapidly at elevated temperatures easily achievable during fires [2, 3]. The structural properties of FRP composite materials have been measured to dramatically decrease at temperatures around the glass transition temperature of resin [1]. For inexpensive polyester and vinyl ester resins typically used in ship construction, the glass transition temperature is typically around 120°C. Maintaining temperatures below the glass transition temperature, thereby protecting the structural integrity of the composite design, would require 100mm of insulation on each face of the laminate [4].

Limited research has been conducted on the structural response and failure of composites during fires. Several studies have examined the structural dependence of laminates to high temperatures [5-9]. These studies have shown that matrix softening and delamination reduce the compression properties. Several engineering models have been developed to determine the effect of compressive loading and one-sided heating on FRP laminates [5-9]. Bausano et al. [5] modeled the response of composites using lamination theory and finite element analysis; however, predictions were limited to

reversible thermal effects and matrix decomposition was not considered. Liu et al. [6] performed an analytical study predicting the thermal buckling and expansion in constrained composite columns with a linear temperature profile. Gibson et al. [8] developed a thermo-mechanical model to predict the degradation of the mechanical properties of a thermally exposed laminate. Gu and Asaro [9] developed an analytical approach to determine the buckling load of a composite with continuously varying material properties, finding good agreement with fire testing data.

A thermo-mechanical model is presented in this paper that combines many of the features of previous mechanical models with a detailed thermal model for accurate prediction of through-thickness temperature response and mechanical properties. The model utilizes a one-dimensional, heat and mass transfer model developed to predict the through-thickness temperature gradient. The predicted temperatures and decomposed state of the laminate were used to calculate the compressive strength and mechanical properties. The mechanical response of the laminate was predicted using an eccentric beam model. An evaluation of the model was performed using a series of four intermediate-scale furnace tests performed on woven glass/vinyl ester laminates. The four tests include the variation of the fire exposure intensity (viz. IMO A.754(18) [10] and UL1709 [11] time-temperature curves) and compressive load levels.

THERMO-MECHANICAL MODEL

A thermo-mechanical model was developed to predict the structural failure of a compressively loaded, heated laminate. Figure 1 contains a schematic showing the details of the one-dimensional thermo-mechanical model. The model assumes uniform heating over the exposed surface area and uniformly applied compressive loads along the width of the laminate. These assumptions allow the laminate to be treated as a one-dimensional system where temperatures and mechanical properties vary only in the through-thickness direction. The thermal model was a one-dimensional heat and mass transfer model used to predict the through-thickness temperature gradient. The one-dimensional mechanical model was developed based on an eccentrically loaded beam. Eccentric loading is caused by the degradation of mechanical properties due to the elevated temperatures and decomposition, resulting in a shift in the neutral axis. As a result, the laminate cannot buckle in the Euler (bifurcation) sense.

Figure 1. (a) Free-body diagram of a portion of the eccentrically loaded column and (b) through-thickness thermal gradient from one-sided heating.

Thermal Model

The thermal model was a one-dimensional heat and mass transfer model based on the governing equations from Lattimer et al. [12]. This includes the energy equation, a model for solid material decomposition, and conservation of mass. The energy equation is provided below:

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + (h + Q - h_g) \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \dot{m}_g'' C_g \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) \quad (1)$$

On the left, the first term is the time-temperature response of the material, the second term is the energy required to decompose the sample, and the third term is the internal convection associated with pyrolysis gas flow inside the material. The term on the right side of the equation relates to heat conduction. In the equation, T , t , and y are the temperature, time, and through-thickness coordinate, respectively, while ρ is the density. The thermal properties, k , C , and C_g , are thermal conductivity, specific heat capacity, and specific heat capacity of the gases, respectively. All thermal properties are defined as functions of temperature and decomposition state. The mass flux of the convective gases is \dot{m}_g'' while Q , h , and h_g are the heat of decomposition, the enthalpy of the laminate, and the enthalpy of the pyrolysis gases, respectively.

The rate of decomposition of the solid material, $\partial\rho/\partial t$, was determined using an n th order Arrhenius kinetics equation

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = -(\rho_v - \rho_d) \left[\frac{\rho - \rho_d}{\rho_v - \rho_d} \right]^n A e^{-E_a/RT} \quad (2)$$

where A , E_a , and n are the pre-exponential factor (rate constant), activation energy, and order of the decomposition reaction, respectively. All of these values must be determined through thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the composite. R is the universal gas constant. The instantaneous, initial, and final (fully decomposed) densities are ρ , ρ_v , and ρ_d , respectively.

The mass flux of gases, \dot{m}_g'' , was determined through an integrated form of the conservation of mass. Assuming all gases generated during decomposition flow to the heated surface, the mass flux of gases from the heated surface is determined by

$$\dot{m}_g''(y', t) = \int_{y'}^L \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} dy \quad (3)$$

where $\partial\rho/\partial t$ is calculated directly using the Arrhenius kinetics equation from Eq. (2). Boundary conditions are defined at both $y=0$ and $y=L$ boundaries of the system as Dirchlet (defined temperature), Neumann (heat flux), or Robin (heat flux, convection, and radiation). Equations (1)-(3) were solved using the Galerkin finite element method. The model provides the temperature response and decomposition of the material.

Mechanical Model

The mechanical model was based on an eccentrically loaded beam [13]. Consider a pin-ended column with a compressive, eccentrically applied load, as seen in Figure 1.

Creating an equivalent force-couple system for the eccentric load, an axial force and bending moment are applied at each end of the column.

Applying beam theory to the free-body diagram shown in Figure 1, the elastic curve equation may be written in terms of the moment developed within the column

$$\frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = -\frac{P}{EI}y - \frac{Pe}{EI} \quad (4)$$

where x and y are the axial and transverse directions, respectively. Applying pinned-pinned boundary conditions, $y=0$ at $x=0$ and $x=L$, to Eq. (4), a solution for the panel deflection was determined:

$$y = e \left(\tan \frac{pL}{2} \sin px + \cos px - 1 \right) \quad (5)$$

The maximum deflection of a pinned-pinned column occurs at the column's mid-height. Therefore, the maximum deflection may be calculated by setting $x=L/2$ in Eq. (5), and after simplification the maximum deflection is expressed as

$$y_{max} = e \left[\sec \left(\sqrt{\frac{P}{EI}} \frac{L}{2} \right) - 1 \right] \quad (6)$$

From Eq. (6), the calculated maximum deflection, y_{max} , becomes infinite as the terms in the secant go to $\pi/2$. However, even though the deflection will not become infinite, it will become unacceptably large and P should not be allowed to reach the critical value that satisfies this condition. Therefore, a critical P is defined

$$P_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{L^2} \quad (7)$$

Substituting this into the equation for y_{max} , the maximum deflection is defined in an alternate form

$$y_{max} = e \left[\sec \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{\frac{P}{P_{cr}}} \right) - 1 \right] \quad (8)$$

The maximum stress of the bending column occurs where the bending moment is at a maximum. This can be obtained through calculation of the normal stresses due to the axial force and bending moment

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{P}{A} + \frac{M_{max}c}{I} \quad (9)$$

where c is the distance from the neutral axis to the outside fibers, I is the moment of inertia, and A is the cross-sectional area. The maximum bending moment, M_{max} , occurs at the location of the maximum deflection of the column. For pinned-pinned end conditions, this occurs at the mid-height of the column. Therefore, substitution for the maximum deflection of the column at the mid-height found in Eq. (8) into the maximum stress equation in Eq. (9) results in

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{P}{A} \left[1 + \frac{ec}{r^2} \sec \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{\frac{P}{P_{cr}}} \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

where r is the radius of gyration and is defined by $r = \sqrt{I/A}$. Eq. (14) may be employed for any column, regardless of end conditions, as long as P_{cr} is calculated properly. Solving Eq. (10) for P_{cr} as defined for varying end conditions according to Euler buckling, maximum stress is determined relative to effective length

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{P}{A} \left[1 + \frac{ec}{r^2} \sec \left(\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{P}{EA}} \frac{L_e}{r} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

where L_e is the effective length of the column, and is defined as 1.0, 0.5, and 0.7 for pinned-pinned, fixed-fixed, and fixed-pinned end conditions, respectively.

In developing a model to determine failure of the laminate, it is observed that the elastic modulus is non-uniform through the thickness of the laminate. The through-thickness gradient of the elastic modulus will cause the neutral axis to shift from the mid-surface. The distance, e , of the neutral axis from the mid-surface is determined from

$$e = \frac{\int_A E(y)y dA}{\int_A E(y) dA} \quad (12)$$

where E is the elastic modulus through the thickness of the laminate. The numerator is the ‘first moment’ of the elastic modulus with respect to the mid-surface and the denominator is the bulk elastic modulus. The shift in the neutral axis causes the scope of the problem to change from a centrally loaded column governed by Euler buckling (bifurcation), to a compressively loaded column developing stresses in bending and axial compression and is governed by beam bending theory.

The elastic modulus and compressive strength are temperature dependent. These properties vary through the laminate thickness due to the thermal gradient during heating. A semi-empirical model [8, 14] was used to provide a relationship between temperature and mechanical properties. The properties remain at a room-temperature value ($P_{(0)}$) until the laminate reaches a critical softening point (T_{cr}). Above this temperature, the property decreases with an increase in temperature to an effective minimum value. The relationship is expressed using the semi-empirical equation [14]

$$P_c(T) = \left(\frac{P_{(0)} + P_{(R)}}{2} - \frac{P_{(0)} + P_{(R)}}{2} \tanh(\Phi(T - T_k)) \right) R_{rc}(T)^n, \quad (13)$$

where Φ is a material constant, effective minimum value $P_{(R)}$, and T_k is the temperature corresponding to 50% remaining of the laminate property. $R_{rc}(T)$ is an empirical scaling function to account for laminate decomposition and is calculated in the thermal model as the instantaneous mass fraction, or percentage of virgin material remaining. The exponent n for this function is an empirical value. Φ , T_k , $P_{(0)}$, and $P_{(R)}$ were determined experimentally using tests on warp-aligned woven glass laminates with unmodified vinyl ester resin (Derakane 411-350) at elevated temperatures. The through thickness properties are calculated using the temperatures predicted from the thermal model. The bulk properties were calculated using numerical integration over the load-bearing cross-section.

The thermal and mechanical models were successively solved to determine the failure of the laminate. The thermal was first used to calculate the laminate temperature gradient. Laminate mechanical properties and compressive strength were then calculated as a function of temperature and decomposition state. The time-to-failure of the laminate was then predicted as the time when the maximum applied compressive stress exceeds the bulk compressive strength of the laminate.

FURNACE TESTS

Four intermediate-scale furnace tests were performed on woven glass/vinyl ester laminates [15]. The laminates used in the tests were made using a 20 ply, quasi-isotropic lay-up with an overall thickness of 12 mm. The laminate was fabricated using plain woven E-glass fabric (800 g/m² Vetrotex Certaineed 324-3B 5:4) and vinyl ester resin (Derakane 510A). Ceramic fiber insulation, 25.4 mm thick, was attached to the exposed face of the laminates. The overall dimensions of the laminates were 0.91 m high and 0.71 m wide.

Tests were performed using an intermediate-scale furnace, described elsewhere [15], capable of imposing standard fire exposures. The internal dimensions of the furnace were 1.22 m (H) x 0.91 m (W) x 0.91 m (D). A hydraulic test frame was mounted to the front of the furnace and was capable of carrying loads of 44.4 kN (10 kips). The top of the test article was mounted in an 18mm wide, 25mm deep U-channel mounting bar, restricting the movement and allowing only vertical translation. The bottom of the test article was also mounted in an 18mm wide, 25mm deep U-channel bar but had a rod on either end for a pin-type connection. This allowed only rotation of the bottom of the test article with no vertical translation. Test articles were placed flush on one side of the channel (furnace side) and then shims were placed in the channel so that the panel fit tightly in the channel.

Test articles were instrumented to measure the thermal and structural response of the sample during the fire exposure. Thermocouples (Type K) were used to measure the through-thickness temperature profiles at the one-third and two-third heights. Linear potentiometers were used to measure the in-plane deflection and out-of-plane deflections at heights of 160, 310, and 620 mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Four tests were performed using the intermediate-scale furnace and test frame. Three tests were performed using an IMO A.754(18) standard fire exposure and were subjected to initial applied loads of 9.7, 9.9, and 4.8 kN. The remaining test was performed using an UL 1709 standard fire exposure and was subjected to a 22.3 kN initial applied load.

The thermo-mechanical model was used to predict the thermal response and time-to-failure of the laminate. Thermal properties and Arrhenius kinetics constants in Eq. (2) were previously determined for E-glass/vinyl ester composites as a function of temperature and decomposition state [12]. The boundary conditions for the one-dimensional model were set at the exposed and unexposed surfaces. The exposed

surface was set to a radiative-convective boundary condition where the emissivity was that of insulation (0.5), the convective heat transfer coefficient was $40 \text{ kW/m}^2\text{-K}$, and the external gas temperature was defined by the standard fire exposure. The unexposed surface was set to the same boundary condition where the emissivity was that of composite (0.9), the convective heat transfer coefficient was $10 \text{ kW/m}^2\text{-K}$, and the external gas temperature was 300 K. Feih [16] determined the constants for use in calculation of the compressive strength and elastic modulus using the semi-empirical relationship in Eq. (4). For calculation of the compressive strength, $\sigma_{c(0)} = 433.3 \text{ MPa}$, $\sigma_{c(R)} = 10 \text{ MPa}$, $\Phi = 0.0264$, and $T_k = 88.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. For calculation of the elastic modulus, $E_{(0)} = 26.8 \text{ GPa}$, $E_{(R)} = 18.2 \text{ GPa}$, $\Phi = 0.0266$, and $T_k = 88.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The load was applied at an initial eccentricity of 3.5mm from the center of the panel due to the shimming of the panel towards the fire. During the course of the exposure, the neutral axis shifted towards the location of the eccentrically applied load. This caused a reduction in the bending of the panel. Continued heating caused the neutral axis to shift away from the applied load location, towards the fire, reapplying the bending of the panel. During longer duration tests, the panel decomposed at the exposed surface, causing the neutral axis to shift towards the location of the eccentrically applied load, resulting in a reduction of the bending of the panel.

Plots of the data and analysis for the IMO A.754(18) exposure at initial loads of 9.7, 9.9, and 4.8 kN are shown in Figures 2, 3, and 4, respectively. A plot of the data and analysis for the UL 1709 exposure at an initial load of 22.3 kN is shown in Figure 5. The time-to-failure can be viewed in Figures 2a to 5a as the time when the maximum stress (dashed lines) is equal to the bulk compressive strength of the laminate (solid lines). A summary of the thermo-mechanical model predictions compared to test data is provided in Table 1. Provided in the table are the predicted and measured times-to-failure as well as the through thickness temperatures profiles at the time of failure measured at the center of the laminate.

Figure 2. Stress versus time (a) for an IMO A.754(18) exposure and a 9.9 kN initial applied load and its predicted (solid lines) and observed (dashed) thermal gradient versus time (b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Stress versus time (a) for an IMO A.754(18) exposure and a 9.7 kN load and its predicted (solid lines) and observed (dashed) thermal gradient versus time (b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Stress versus time (a) for an IMO A.754(18) exposure and a 4.8 kN initial applied load and its predicted (solid lines) and observed (dashed) thermal gradient versus time (b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Stress versus time (a) for a UL 1709 exposure and a 22.3 kN load and its predicted (solid lines) and observed (dashed) thermal gradient versus time (b).

Table 1. Comparison of predictions against furnace tests with compressive loading.

Test No.	Furnace Exposure	Load (kN)	Time-to-Failure (min)		1/3 laminate thickness (°C)		2/3 laminate thickness (°C)		Unexposed Surface (°C)	
			Pred.	Data	Pred	Data	Pred	Data	Pred	Data
1	IMO A.754(18)	Note 1.	46.0	45.8	236	196	194	168	158	154
2	IMO A.754(18)	9.9	94.4	62.7	341	244	278	212	221	181
3	IMO A.754(18)	Note 2.	101.7	98.9	351	255	284	219	225	188
4	UL 1709	22.3	19.1	11.3	246	158	190	133	151	114

Note 1. Sample subjected to 9.7 kN load for 40 min. then increased until failure at 21.4 kN

Note 2. Sample subjected to 4.8 kN load for 95.5 min. then increased until failure at 7.2 kN

The temperature profiles predicted by the model, shown in Figures 2b to 5b, agree reasonably well with the recorded test data. A discrepancy exists for the temperatures at the interface of the insulation and laminate, which is attributed to measurement error. Due to the large temperature gradients at this location, a small offset of the thermocouple from the surface can result in a large temperature difference. The predicted maximum stress in the laminates, shown in Figures 2a to 5a, behaves as expected. The maximum stress increases as the laminate mechanical properties degrade which causes the neutral axis to shift. This leads to an increase in the eccentricity of the applied load, which, according to Eq. (15), will cause an increase in the maximum stress. Tests 1 and 3 show good agreement between the predicted and measured times-to-failure. Predicted times-to-failure for Tests 2 and 4, however, show a discrepancy of 10 to 30 minutes with the experimental times-to-failure. This is attributed to the absence of thermal expansion in the thermo-mechanical model. Thermal expansion causes the laminate to expand; however, the applied compressive load restricts the axial expansion of the laminate. Therefore, the laminate experiences additional out-of-plane bending and develops added stresses due to the increased bending. The thermal expansion will ultimately cause the laminate to fail prior to the thermo-mechanical model predictions due to the absence of this effect.

CONCLUSION

A thermo-mechanical model was developed to predict the time-to-failure of FRP laminates under combined compressive loading and thermal exposure due to fire. The model employs a one-dimensional, heat and mass transfer model. Predicted temperatures are then used to calculate the degradation of the compressive strength and elastic modulus through a semi-empirical relationship. The degradation of the mechanical properties in the laminate causes a shift in the neutral axis; therefore, the solutions for an eccentrically loaded beam were used to determine the maximum stress in the laminate due to compressive loading. The model was used to predict results from a series of four intermediate-scale tests performed using a furnace with standard fire exposures on a compressively loaded panel. The model predicted the through-thickness temperature gradient reasonably well for all tests. The predicted times-to-failure for two tests with ramped loading conditions showed good agreement with test data. However, the model over predicted the times-to-failure for two constant loading conditions. This was attributed to not including thermal expansion in the thermo-mechanical model.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the funding support from the Office of Naval Research, Contract No. N00014-07-1-0514. The authors would also like to thank Dr. Scott Case for discussions regarding different aspects of this work.

References

1. Couchman, L. and A. Mouritz, eds. *Modeling of naval composite structures in fire*. 2006, Acclaim Printing Services, Ltd.: Templestowe, Victoria, Australia.
2. Egglestone, G.T. and D.M. Turley, *Flammability of GRP for use in ship structures*. Fire Mater, 1994. 18: p. 255-60.
3. Fisher, K.J., *Is fire a barrier to shipboard composites*. Adv Compos, 1993. (May/June): p. 20-6.
4. Beeston, A., *Reducing the weight of structural fire protection in composite ships*. BrandPosten, 2006. 34.
5. Bausano, J.V., J.J. Lesko, and S.W. Case, *Composite life under sustained compression and one sided simulated fire exposure: Characterization and prediction*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2006. 37(7): p. 1092-1100.
6. Liu, L., et al., *Thermal buckling of a heat-exposed, axially restrained composite column*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2006. 37(7): p. 972-980.
7. Zhou, A. and T. Keller, *Structural response of FRP elements under combined thermal and mechanical loading: experiments and analysis*, in *4th conference on composites in fire*. 2005: Newcastle-upon-Tyne, UK.
8. Gibson, A.G., et al., *Laminate theory analysis of composites under load in fire*. Journal of Composite Materials, 2006. 40(7): p. 639-658.
9. Gu, P. and R.J. Asaro, *Structural buckling of polymer matrix composites due to reduced stiffness from fire damage*. Composite Structures, 2005. 69: p. 65-75.
10. IMO_Resolution_A.754(18), *Recommendation on Fire Resistance Tests for "A", "B", and "F" Class Division*, in *FTP Code - International Code for Application of Fire Test Procedures*. 1998, International Maritime Organization.
11. UL1709, *Rapid rise fire tests of protection materials for structural steel*. 1991, Underwriters Laboratories, Inc.: Northbrook, IL.
12. Lattimer, B.Y., J. Ouellette, and J. Trelles, *Thermal Response of Composite Materials to Elevated Temperatures*, in *Modeling of Naval Composite Structures in Fire*, C. L and M. A, Editors. 2006, Acclaim Printing Services, Inc.: Templestowe, Victoria, Australia.
13. Beer, F.P., et al., *Mechanics of Materials*. Fifth ed. 2009, New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
14. Feih, S., et al., *Modelling the tension and compression strengths of polymer laminates in fire*. Composites Science and Technology, 2007. 67(3-4): p. 551-564.
15. Lattimer, B.Y., et al., *Structural Response of Fiber Reinforced Plastic Composites During Fires*. 2007.
16. Feih, S., *Personal Communication*. 2008.